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A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF EMPLOYEES IN RELIANCE MARKET AT TIRUNELVELI

C. Priya ¹

Dr. P. Geetha ²

Abstract

In today's competitive world, a great majority of organizations are focusing their resources and placing great emphasis on talent acquisition and retention so that they are at pace with their peers and to keep their employees highly motivated and satisfied. Job satisfaction is an essential part of an employee's lifecycle and sustains his motivation and loyalty towards his organization. This observational and interaction based study has been done with the purpose of understanding the current level of job satisfaction among employees of Reliance Market in Tirunelveli and their influencing factors.

1. Introduction

Job satisfaction of an employee is the positive feeling that they have towards their job. Higher the level of employee satisfaction higher the commitment and motivation levels shown by the employee towards their job. Job satisfaction of an employee is a virtue that can be influenced by a variety of factors, e.g. the financial & social status of the current organization, the quality of one's relationship with their superior, the physical environment effect in which they work and the degree of involvement and fulfillment in their work, etc.

2. Objectives of the study

- To study the job satisfaction levels of employees working in Reliance market, Tirunelveli.
- To understand the level of importance shown by the organization to improve & develop employee satisfaction.
- To understand & rate the employee's view of various organizational activities & their effect on employee satisfaction.

3. Limitations of the study

- This study is limited to the employees working in Reliance Market, Tirunelveli.
- This empirical study is based on and limits itself to 50 randomly collected samples from respondents, currently employed in Reliance Market.
- Primary data has been collected through Direct Questionnaire.

¹ Ph.D. Scholar, Reg. No. 19111191012002, PG and Research Department of Commerce, Sadakathullah Appa College (Autonomous), Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli 627 012, Tamil Nadu, India.

² Assistant Professor, PG and Research Department of Commerce, Sadakathullah Appa College (Autonomous), Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli 627 012, Tamil Nadu, India.

4. Methodology:

- This section attempts to describe the methodology of the present study. It includes period of the study, sampling techniques, collection of data and tools of analysis of data.

4.1 Area & Place of Study Profile

- Tirunelveli is now a bee-hive for upcoming super markets and food chains. One such super market chain (Reliance market) opened in the year 2014 and is situated in centre of the city(Vannarapettai) and is easily approachable by all means of transport. Around 200 people are employed in reliance market working in 3 shifts (24*7) across different departments.

4.2 Sampling Design

- The data collected are original in nature. For the collection of data, one hundred employees were selected as respondents by convenience random sampling method.

4.3 Statistical tools for analysis

- Tabulation
- Percentage
- Mean score analysis
- Garrett Ranking

5. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Analysis on the Demographic factors

Sl. No.	Demographic Factors	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	31	62
		Female	19	38
2	Age Group	21 - 30 years	18	36
		31 - 40 years	22	44
		41 - 50 years	8	16
		Above 50 years	2	4
3	Qualification	Up to School level	6	12
		Diploma Holder	6	12
		Degree Holder	35	70
		Post Graduate	3	6
4	Income Group	Up to ₹ 10,000	14	28
		₹ 10000 - 20000	14	28
		₹ 20000 - 30000	10	20
		Above 30000	7	14
		Above 40000	5	10
5	Experience Level	Less than 6 months	2	4
		6 months - 1 year	12	24
		2 - 5 years	17	34
		More than 5 years	19	38

Source: Primary Data.

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. There are 62% of male respondents and 38% of female respondents who have participated in the survey. Majority of respondents 44% are in age group of 31-40 years, 36% of respondents are between 21-30 years, 16% of respondents between 41-50 years and 4% of respondents are more than 50 years. On educational qualification, 12% of respondents have finished schooling, 12% are diploma holders, majority (70%) of the respondents are degree holders while 6% are post graduates. The above table reveals that 28% of respondents come under income group up to ₹ 10000, 28% of respondents between ₹ 10000-20000, 20% of respondents between ₹ 20000-30000, 14% of respondents above ₹ 30000 and 10% of respondents above ₹ 40000. According to this table 4% of employees are having experience of less than 6 months, 24% of respondents are having experience of 6 months to 1 year, 34% of respondents are having 2-5 years of experience level, majority of respondents 38% are having more than 5 years of experience level.

Table 2: Organizational Activities

Sl. No.	Organizational behavior	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied	Total
a)	Recognition of Achievements	6 (12)	22 (44)	15 (30)	3 (6)	4 (8)	50 (100)
b)	Rewarding overtime	4 (8)	21 (42)	14 (28)	6 (12)	5 (10)	50 (100)
c)	Satisfaction with salary	3 (6)	17 (34)	14 (28)	8 (16)	8 (16)	50 (100)
d)	Praised in front of seniors	3 (6)	30 (60)	14 (28)	1 (2)	2 (4)	50 (100)
e)	Non- monetary incentives.	5 (1)	28 (56)	12 (24)	3 (6)	2 (4)	50 (100)
f)	Promotion of employees	12 (24)	17 (34)	8 (16)	7 (14)	6 (12)	50 (100)

Source: Computed Primary data

From the above table, five-point scale question have been taken for survey. Majority of respondents 44% are satisfied when the organization recognizes their achievements while 30% are neutral and 12% are highly satisfied. In case of rewarding overtime 42% of respondents are satisfied, 28% of respondents are in neutral and 12% are dissatisfied. Majority of respondents 34% are satisfied with their salary, 28% of respondents are in neutral and 16% of respondents are highly dissatisfied. Majority of respondents 60% are satisfied that they are praised in front of seniors, while 28% are neutral. 56% of the respondents are satisfied that the organization provides adequate non-monetary incentives while 34% & 24% of the

respondents are satisfied and highly satisfied respectively that their organization promotes employees who perform well.

Table 3: Working Atmosphere

Sl. No.	Organizational activities	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied	Total
a)	Good & Neat Workplace	11 (22)	19 (38)	13 (26)	7 (14)	0 (0)	50 (100)
b)	Welcoming New Ideas	9 (18)	19 (38)	14 (28)	8 (16)	0 (0)	50 (100)
c)	Employee safety	13 (26)	17 (34)	15 (30)	2 (4)	3 (6)	50 (100)
d)	Individual development	9 (18)	12 (24)	14 (28)	9 (18)	6 (12)	50 (100)

Source: Computed Primary data

Table 3 five-point scale question has been taken regarding the working atmosphere of employees. Majority of respondents 38% are satisfied that their organization has provided a good and neat workplace, 26% are neutral while 22% of respondents are highly satisfied and 14% of respondents are dissatisfied. In case of welcoming new ideas 38% of respondents are satisfied, 28% of respondents are in neutral and 16% are dissatisfied. Majority of respondents 34% are satisfied with their employee safety, 30% of respondents are in neutral and 18% of respondents are dissatisfied. The survey reveals 28% of respondents are in neutral that the organization shows importance to their individual development, 24% of respondents are satisfied and 18% are dissatisfied.

Table 5.4: Monetary Benefits

Sl. No.	Monetary Benefit	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied	Total
a)	Salary remittance	10 (20)	14 (28)	15 (30)	7 (14)	4 (8)	50 (100)
b)	Extra time wages	11 (22)	15 (30)	15 (30)	5 (10)	4 (8)	50 (100)
c)	PF/ESI payment	11 (22)	12 (24)	17 (34)	6 (12)	4 (8)	50 (100)
d)	Medical reimbursement	10 (20)	12 (24)	17 (34)	8 (16)	3 (6)	50 (100)

Source: Computed Primary data

From the above table 5.4, majority of respondents 30% are in neutral in case of on-time salary remittance, 28% of respondents are satisfied and 14% of respondents are dissatisfied. In providing extra wages 30% of respondents are both satisfied and neutral. 22% of respondents are highly satisfied and 10% are dissatisfied. Majority of respondents 34% are in neutral for PF/ESI payment regularly, 24% of respondents are satisfied while 22% are highly satisfied and 12% of respondents are dissatisfied. In case of medical reimbursement, 34% of respondents are in neutral, 24% of

respondents are satisfied, 20% of respondents are highly satisfied and 16% of respondents are dissatisfied.

Table 5: Leave Policy

Sl. No.	Organizational Activity	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied	Total
a)	Weekly offs provided regularly	11 (22)	11 (22)	15 (30)	9 (18)	4 (8)	50 (100)
b)	Casual / Sick leave provided as entitled	10 (20)	12 (24)	14 (28)	10 (20)	4 (8)	50 (100)
c)	Transparency in Leave policy	10 (20)	11 (22)	17 (34)	9 (18)	3 (6)	50 (100)
d)	Maternity leave provision (Women)	11 (22)	13 (26)	16 (32)	7 (14)	3 (6)	50 (100)

Source: Computed Primary data

Table 5.5 discusses the effect of leave policy of employees working in reliance market. Majority of respondents 30% are neutral in case of weekly offs provided to them while 22% each of respondents are both satisfied and highly satisfied and 18% of respondents are dissatisfied. In case of casual/sick leave 28% of respondents are neutral and 24% of respondents are satisfied, 20% are highly satisfied and 20% of respondents are dissatisfied. Transparency in leave policy showed 34% of respondents are neutral, 22% of respondents are satisfied, 20% of respondents are highly satisfied and 18% are dissatisfied. In case of women employee 32% of respondents are neutral that the organization provides maternity leave, 26% of respondents are satisfied, 22% of respondents are highly satisfied and 14% of respondents are dissatisfied.

Table 5.6 Basic Working Conditions

Sl. No.	Particulars	Weighted Garrett Score	Weighted average Garrett Score	Rank
1	Recognition & Rewards	3324	66.48	I
2	Nice Work Environment	3297	65.94	II
3	Monetary Benefits	2906	58.12	III
4	Leave Policy	2831	56.62	IV
5	Working Hours	2314	46.28	V
6	Encouraging Superiors	2269	45.38	VI
7	Self-Initiation	1951	39.02	VII
8	Others	1108	22.16	VIII

Source: Computed Primary Data

On the basis of Garrett ranking among organizational behavior of respondents, recognition and rewards scored I rank to be rated as the most preferred behavior in job satisfaction, Nice work environment scored II rank, Monetary benefits scored III rank, Leave policy scored IV rank, Working hours scored V rank, encouraging superiors scored VI rank, self-

initiation scored VII rank and other option preferred VIII rank for the respondents in the organization.

6. Suggestions

- Organizational activities such as rewarding achievements & praising employees in front of colleagues can be further improved to improve employee motivation.
- Although great emphasis has been given to employee safety & individual development both can still be improved upon to involve & motivate employees. Superior's encouragement & active involvements in team decisions can still be further improved
- Satisfaction levels on monetary benefits are high although organization can look into betterment on medical reimbursement to further enhance the employee potential.
- Satisfaction levels on leave policy are high although organization can look into transparency & easing of leave policy to encourage employee involvement.
- Organization to focus more on motivation of self-involvement & superior engagements with employees to enhance employee satisfaction potential.

7. Conclusion

- The present study on employee satisfaction in Reliance Market, Tirunelveli reveals that job satisfaction levels among employees are relatively high with employees satisfied with various organizational activities.
- Organizational activities such as rewarding achievements & praising employees in front of colleagues can be further improved to improve employee motivation.
- Although great emphasis has been given to employee safety & individual development both can be improved upon to involve & motivate employees.
- Superior's encouragement & active involvements in team decisions can still be improved.
- Satisfaction levels on monetary benefits are high although organization can look into betterment on medical reimbursement to further enhance the employee potential.
- Satisfaction levels on leave policy are high although organization can look into transparency & easing of leave policy to encourage employee involvement.
- Organization to focus more on motivation of self-involvement & superior engagements with employees to enhance employee satisfaction potential.

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